

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN REAL ESTATE MANAGEMENT AND WAYS OF ITS IMPLEMENTATION IN OUR COUNTRY

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Annotation. The article presents practical proposals to adapt foreign experiences to national conditions in order to improve the management of Uzbekistan's real estate facilities. This work is aimed at solving pressing scientific and practical problems aimed at improving the efficiency of the real estate market, improving the investment environment and ensuring economic stability.

Keywords: real estate management, foreign experience, digital technologies, environmental principles, national economy.

Annotatsiya. Maqola O'zbekistonning ko'chmas mulk obyektlarini boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirish uchun xorijiy tajribalarni milliy sharoitlarga moslashtirish bo'yicha amaliy takliflarni taqdim etadi. Ushbu ish ko'chmas mulk bozorining samaradorligini oshirish, investitsion muhitni yaxshilash va iqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta'minlashga qaratilgan dolzarb ilmiy-amaliy muammolarni hal qilishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ko'chmas mulkni boshqarish, xorijiy tajriba, raqamli texnologiyalar, ekologik tamoyillar, milliy iqtisodiyot.

Аннотация. В статье представлены практические предложения по адаптации зарубежного опыта к национальным условиям совершенствования системы управления объектами недвижимости Узбекистана. Данная работа направлена на решение актуальных научно-практических задач, направленных на повышение эффективности рынка недвижимости, улучшение инвестиционного климата и обеспечение экономической стабильности.

Ключевые слова: управление недвижимостью, зарубежный опыт, цифровые технологии, экологические принципы, национальная экономика.

Introduction. Currently, the real estate sector is one of the strategically important sectors of the economy. The effective functioning of the real estate market not only provides social stability, but also serves to improve the investment climate, create new jobs and increase income to the state budget. Therefore, the issues of managing real estate facilities have become one of the pressing issues of today. Experience of foreign countries shows that the use of modern management methods and technologies significantly increases the effectiveness of this industry. In particular, management models formed in the states of the United States, Europe and Asia are an important factor in the sustainable development of the real estate market. By studying these experiences and adapting them to the conditions of Uzbekistan, it is possible to define new prospects for the development of the national real estate sector.

Analysis of thematic literature. Real estate management activities are a relatively new area of formation in the Republic. Today, there are research works written by a number of foreign and Uzbek scientists related to the topic of the research work. In particular, scientific

work related to the management of real estate objects has been carried out by a number of foreign scientists edge. Mac-Lin, N. Orduy, Dj. Friedman, Dj. Trump, A. Sukerman, Dj. D. Blevins, GB. Reflected in the scientific research of the eddreds and others [1].

Scientists of the CIS countries A.N. Asaul, I.T. Balabanov, A.G. Gryaznova, V.V. Ivanov, I.I. Mazur, S.N. Maksimov, A.B. Marchenko, V.Z. Chernyak., S.A. Lomakina has made significant contributions to the coverage of the real estate property management issue [2].

Some problems of management of real estate objects in Uzbekistan M.A. Ikramov, M. Mirakhmedov, V.U. Yadavov, D. Ya. Butunov, T.A. Khasanov, Sh.A. Isamukhamedova, R.I. Studied in the scientific research work of Nurimbetov and others [3]. The above Foreign and Uzbek scientists have carried out a lot of research work in the field of real estate market, management and assessment of real estate objects. At the same time, the essence and significance of improving the methodology of managing real estate objects is not fully revealed.

Research methodology. In this article, various methods of scientific research were used in the study of methods and problems of managing real estate objects. In the course of the study, qualitative and quantitative research methods were used in harmony and analytical data was brought on the basis of the application of each method to this topic.

Analysis and results. One of the most important factors affecting the socio-economic condition of the country in the way of life of its inhabitants, living a prosperous life, is the provision of the population's need for primary real estate objects. The fact that residents have their own housing directly affects the processes that determine the socio-demographic and way of living. When the lack of housing for the population in any country or the formation of an unfavorable infrastructure creates a negative environment for any family, as a result of which a mood of discontent is formed in the population. As factors that shape the mood of discontent in the population, the following can be noted: the absence of favorable infrastructure in populated areas; poor planning of the transport structure, low housing stock in relation to the population, or the fact that the demand for real estate objects is extremely high, the unemployment rate is high; shortage of clean drinking water; high demand for energy resources; unsatisfactory state of population recreation and health system; poor service system by region, etc. Each person wishes that in his place of residence there will be conditions favorable to him.

The experience of foreign countries has shown that positive results in effective management from the housing stock can be adapted to our country. At the same time, it will be necessary to form our own model of organizing the management of real estate objects in the field of Housing and communal services in our country. To do this, it will be necessary to group Common Problems in the management of Housing and communal services and develop measures in the population for problems that are part of each group. The solution to the problems is to adapt the industry to market principles. But when solving certain types of problems, it will be necessary to look at the social situation of the population.

Focusing on the practice of the countries of the world, the provision of the population with real estate objects, the management of housing funds have always organized complex processes. In the developed countries of today's Kur, competitive relations have formed in the field of management of housing funds. That is, the management of housing funds is considered at the entrepreneurial level, and this type of activity is a source of income. In the developing

world, however, it has been the subject of much Islami regarding the management of real estate facilities. Therefore, state regulation and financial support for this area continue.

The state of Housing and communal services in some large urban areas is of concern to the population. According to the results of the Center for Strategic Studies of the Russian Federation, the state of high deterioration of Housing and communal infrastructure was 84 percent.

Focusing on the results of the study, the highest figure was a high deterioration in housing and communal infrastructure-84 percent. The rest are divided by percentage as follows: low financial provision of the city – 66 %; absence of large enterprises in the urban area – 40 %; absence / low level of development of high - tech enterprises-34 %; low level of development of transport infrastructure-25%; Primary Care – 17%; high unemployment - 16 %; low citizen participation in the development of the city – 15 %; lack of culture and recreation centers – 14 %; other factors – 6 %; inefficient use of the city God - was 3% (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Problems of socio-economic development of cities

focusing on the experiences of the Swedish state in terms of the formation of real estate objects, in this case, the composition of the owners in terms of their composition than in other states is shown in Figure 2. The picture shows the structure of the housing stock in Sweden and its composition by the category of owners. According to this, in the Swedish state, we can see that the property of enterprises and housing companies-60.10 percent, the property of housing cooperatives – 2.30 percent, private property-16.20 percent, communal housing fund – 21.50 percent.

Figure 2. Structure and structure of the housing fund in Sweden by the category of owners

The share in GDP of the volume of housing development of the population, housing construction, construction of infrastructure facilities, in particular construction work carried

out in countries of the world, is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The share of the construction sector in GDP in countries of the world (in 2023%)

The figure above shows the share of the construction sector in GDP in the countries of the world. Focusing on the results, France – 7.9 percent, Germany – 6.3 percent, Italy – 7.8 percent, Holland – 7.5 percent, USA – 6.3 percent, China – 10.1 percent, England – 9.1 percent, Turkey – 8.1 percent, Kazakh izton – 8.2 percent, Malazia – 7.2 percent, Russia -5.9 percent.

From the experiences of developed countries of the world are always considered important for developing countries. The housing stock management system in foreign countries is shown in Table 1.

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Housing stock management system in foreign countries

№	Country name	Organizations with Real Estate Facilities Management System
1	USA	Territorial associations of the population – Planning Unit Developments (RUD), kondominiumlar – Condominium Association
2	Kanada	Housing Cooperatives
3	France	Syndicat
4	Finland	Apartment Joint Stock Companies
5	Ukraine	Associations of owners of multi-apartment houses - (OSMD)
6	Russia	Homeowners management companies and housing construction cooperatives –(TSJ) va (JSK)

Table 1 of the above shows the system of management of housing stock in foreign countries. Today, in the management of housing funds in the Republic of Uzbekistan, private owners are managed by management companies. But the maintenance of multi-apartment houses, in the work of the katipal and current repairs, is provided with financial funds from the state.

The number of organizations engaged in the management of the housing fund on the example of the city of Tashkent in our country is presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Number of organizations engaged in the management of housing stock in Tashkent

№	District name	Management Tashkent number	Number of multi-storey residential buildings
1	Bektemir	4	179
2	Mirzo Ulug'bek	35	683
3	Almazor	15	655
4	Sergeli	15	622
5	Uch tepa	20	583
6	Chilonzor	26	1232
7	Shayhontohur	21	658
8	Yunusobod	21	927
9	Yakkasaroy	16	407
10	Yangihayot	12	899
11	Yashnoobod	17	1061
	Total	202	9231

The table shows the number of organizations engaged in the management of the housing stock in the city of Tashkent. According to this, the management transportation of 202 housing stock in the city of Tashkent is majud, which serves 9231 multi-storey residential buildings. According to the table, the most managerial organization is the existing Chilonzor district, in which 26 management organizations serve 1,232 residential buildings, the least is Bektemir district, in which 4 management organizations serve 179 residential buildings.

Focusing on World Statistics, more than 1.8 billion people on earth do not have enough housing, approximately 15 million are forced out every year, and 150 million live in homelessness. According to the Housing and Land Rights Network (HLRN), between January and March 2022, 24 people were left homeless in India every hour due to the third wave of the COVID-19 pandemic. In the country, more than 1 million people were displaced from their homes in 2017-2022, and more than 15 million people live daily at risk of being displaced from their homes.

"The EU states have their own housing in two parts of 3/2 of the population. In the European Union in 2021, 70% of the population lived in self-contained housing and the remaining 30% lived in rented housing. The highest property shares were observed in Romania (95% of the population lived in households with their own home), Slovakia (92%, 2021 data), Hungary (92%) and Croatia (91%). Private ownership is common in all EU member states except Germany, with only the rental population in Germany being slightly more common, with just over 50% of the population living on rent. These are followed by Austria (46%) and Denmark (41%)".

During the study, it is advisable to widely use the experience of developed countries in improving the organizational and economic mechanism of managing housing funds. These consist of:

- create favorable conditions for companies and organizations engaged in the management of real estate facilities, give their consumers opportunities to increase the range of additional services;
- depending on the potential of the regions and the financial capabilities of the population, it is necessary to develop mechanisms for the gradual transition of management companies serving housing from a system of state financing to a system of self-independent financial provision;
- creation and implementation of the legal framework for the formation of supervisory boards made up of people active in the activities of the organization managing apartment buildings;
- formation of a database on consumers in the further development of electroon management features in the real estate Object Management System;
- development of stimulating mechanisms for the implementation of payments for housing and communal services and the transition to a strict collection system in cases of non-payment of payments on a regular basis;
- development of population-friendly conditions and incentive mechanisms for Real Estate Facilities Management reforms;
- in the organization of companies and organizations engaged in the management of real estate facilities, the introduction of requirements for a clear definition of the level of understanding of the industry, the potential of expertise and experience;
- effective implementation of modern information technologies for preventing corruption in the field of development and regulation of a system for monitoring the state of execution of tasks set out in legislative documents on the management of real estate facilities.

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